

Synthetic, Spectral, Thermal and Powder X-ray Diffraction Studies on some Coordination Polymers of Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II)

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Manuscript received 31 August 1993

Three new bis-ligands, viz. sebacyl-bis-hydroxamic acid (SHA), adipyl-bis-hydroxamic acid (AHA) and fumaryl-bis-hydroxamic acid (FHA) and their coordination polymers with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have been prepared. These coordination polymers have been characterised by elemental analysis, thermal, infrared spectral and X-ray diffraction studies. These polymers have considerable thermal stability and are insoluble in almost all common organic solvents. Thermogravimetric curves have been analysed critically and discussed in detail. The use of Freeman-Carroll and Sharp-Wentworth methods have been made to evaluate activation energy and thermal stability of these polymers. The values of thermal activation energy calculated with the help of both these methods are in good agreement. Thermodynamic parameters such as free energy change, entropy change, apparent entropy change and the frequency factor have also been evaluated by using the data of Freeman-Carroll method. The decomposition pattern observed on the TGA curves, have been analysed and the conclusions drawn have been further confirmed by DTA studies.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies have been undertaken to determine lattice parameters viz. crystal system, crystal lattice edge, volume and crystallite size.

Considerable amount of work has been reported from these laboratories on the synthetic, structural and thermal studies of several coordination polymers¹⁻³. The interaction between metal ions and ligands may lead to the formation of coordination polymers in which the chelated metal ions are bridged by ligand molecules^{4,5}. The formation of macromolecular chain may be

expected for a ligand with two chelating sites which, for steric reasons, cannot interact with the same metal ions⁶. The present communication describes synthetic, thermal, structural and spectral aspects of the coordination polymers of substituted bis-hydroxamic acids with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} . It also describes the powder X-ray diffraction studies of these polymers.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED-BIS-HYDROXAMIC ACID AND THEIR POLYMERS WITH Zn^{II} AND Cd^{II}

Compd.	M.p./ decomp. temp. (°C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
SHA	120	50.90 (51.72)	8.48 8.62	14.67 14.00	—
AHA	168	41.8 (40.91)	7.00 6.81	15.62 15.90	—
FHA	264	25.05 (26.31)	3.38 3.29	19.06 19.37	—
$\{[Zn^{II}(SHA)].2H_2O\}_n$	300	36.03 (35.86)	6.06 5.97	6.20 5.98	20.81 21.18
$\{[Cd^{II}(SHA)].2H_2O\}_n$	330	32.57 (33.00)	5.26 4.90	5.36 5.30	29.47 30.00
$\{[Zn^{II}(AHA)].2H_2O\}_n$	280	25.99 (25.00)	4.33 3.80	8.00 7.40	24.46 25.00
$\{[Cd^{II}(AHA)].2H_2O\}_n$	340	21.02 (20.50)	3.00 2.80	6.04 5.60	34.86 35.68
$\{[Zn^{II}(FHA)].2H_2O\}_n$	320	19.43 (20.00)	1.82 1.60	9.33 10.28	26.31 27.00
$\{[Cd^{II}(FHA)].2H_2O\}_n$	320	16.32 (16.00)	1.34 1.20	9.52 9.00	38.99 40.00

Results and Discussion

Composition of the polymeric unit : The composition of the polymeric unit was assigned on the basis of detailed study of elemental analysis (Table 1). The presence of water of crystallisation was ascertained on the basis of thermal studies. The composition of the polymeric unit is the same for all the polymers, $\{[M(n)]L.2H_2O\}_n$, where $M = Zn^{II}$ or Cd^{II} and $L = SHA$ or AHA or FHA .

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL FREQUENCIES (IN cm^{-1}) OF SUBSTITUTED-BIS-HYDROXAMIC ACIDS AND THEIR COORDINATION POLYMERS WITH Zn^{II} AND Cd^{II}

SHA	Zn^{II} -SHA	Cd^{II} -SHA	Band assignment
—	3 419	3 243	H—OH (lattice water)
3 264	—	—	OH
1 662	1 554	1 563	C=O at C=O→M site
967	1 028	1 057	—N—O
—	619	618	—O—M
AHA	Zn^{II} -AHA	Cd^{II} -AHA	Band assignment
—	3 429	3 259	H—OH (lattice water)
3 257	—	—	OH
1 661	1 552	1 606	C=O at C=O→M site
971	996	982	—N—O
—	619	665	—O—M
FHA	Zn^{II} -FHA	Cd^{II} -FHA	Band assignment
—	3 424	3 433	H—OH (lattice water)
3 205	—	—	OH
2 900	2 840	2 856	—NH
1 715	1 540	1 584	C=O at C=O→M site
997	1 047	1 005	—N—O
—	600	616	—O—M

Spectral studies : On comparing the infrared spectra of various coordination polymers, it is inferred that they are virtually identical with each other. The assignment of the frequencies for different groups in the polychelates, corresponding to those considered for ligands, have been proposed on the basis of present study and they have been further confirmed on the basis of information available for similar system reported in literature.

The infrared spectra of all the ligands show a band in the range $3\ 205$ – $3\ 264\ cm^{-1}$ which is attributed to the presence of O—H group⁷. This band disappears in coordination polymers indicating the formation of —O—M bond. This suggests the

formation of chelate ring through the oxygen of the ligand with the release of the proton of —O—H group⁸. The medium band appearing at $1\ 661$ – $1\ 715\ cm^{-1}$ in these ligands, is assigned to C=O group which gets lowered down in the coordination polymers, indicating that the oxygen of C=O group takes part in the formation of chelate ring resulting into —C=O → M coordination bond. The medium band appearing at 967 – $997\ cm^{-1}$ (in ligands) is assigned to —N—O stretching vibration which gets shifted to slightly higher region in the coordination polymers with the increase of the intensity. This shifting may be due to the formation of metal-oxygen bond of the type —N—O—M. A new weak band appearing in the spectra of all the coordination polymers in the region 600 – $665\ cm^{-1}$, is due to the O—M stretching frequency. This band is absent in the spectra of the ligands. It is further noted that all the coordination polymers contain a weak to medium intensity band at $3\ 243$ – $3\ 451\ cm^{-1}$, which is due to H—OH vibration and is attributed to the presence of lattice water molecules.

Thus, from the above discussion and from the consideration of potential donor atoms of the polyligands, it can be concluded that the substituted-bis-hydroxamic acids act as bidentate ligands and participate in bonding through the phenolic oxygen and the oxygen of the C=O group to give neutral linear chain coordination polymers. This is confirmed, directly and indirectly, from the following changes observed in the infrared spectra of the substituted-hydroxamic acids, and their coordination polymers with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} : (i) OH band observed in the ligands, disappears in coordination polymers, (ii) C=O stretching frequency of the ligands, shifts towards lower region in the coordination polymers, (iii) a new band corresponding to metal-oxygen stretching frequency appears in coordination polymers, (iv) a new band appears in coordination polymers indicating the presence of water of crystallisation, and (v) —N=O stretching frequency observed in the ligands gets shifted on higher side in coordination polymers.

The infrared spectral assignment of ligands and coordination polymers are tabulated in Table 2. The similarity of ir spectra of all the coordination polymers indicates that the mode of coordination of the ligand is same in all the cases irrespective of metal ions present. On the basis of these studies, the

position of the chelate rings in coordination polymers is in Fig. 1.

R = (CH₂)₈ for sebacyl, (CH₂)₄ for adipyl and (CH₂) for fumarly and M stands for Zn^{II} or Cd^{III}.

Fig. 1. Position of chelate ring in polymers.

Thermal studies : Freeman-Carroll⁹ and Sharp-Wentworth¹⁰ methods have been used to determine the kinetic parameters of the coordination polymers with the help of dynamic TG curves. The usefulness of Freeman-Carroll method is that the parameters of temperature and time can be varied and at the same time the order of reaction and energy of activation can be obtained by a single experiment.

Freeman-Carroll method : The following expression is used to evaluate various kinetic parameters,

$$\frac{\Delta \log(dw/dt)}{\Delta \log(w_r)} = \frac{(-E_a)}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{\Delta 1/T}{\Delta \log w_r} + n$$

This shows that a plot of $\frac{\Delta \log(dw/dt)}{\Delta \log w_r}$ against

$\Delta(1/T)/\Delta \log w_r$ will give an intercept of the y-axis at $x = 0$, which is equal to the value of n (the order of reaction) and a slope $m = -E_a/2.303R$. In the expression given above, $w_r = w_c - w$, where w_c is the weight-loss at the completion of the reaction or at a definite time, w the total weight-loss upto time t , dw/dt the weight-loss with time t , and T the temperature.

Sharp-Wentworth method : The following expression is used to evaluate the activation energy by this method,

$$\frac{\log(dc/dt)}{1-c} = \log(A/B) \cdot \frac{-E_a}{2.303} \cdot \frac{1}{T}$$

where, dc/dt is the fraction of mass loss with time t , T the temperature and $B = dT/dt$.

The presence of water of crystallisation was ascertained on the basis of TGA and DTA studies. The results obtained for different polymers are summarised below. For brevity, only representative

thermal degradation curves for Zn-SHA has been shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. TGA curve for {[Zn^{II}(SHA)].2H₂O}_n.

(i) {[Zn^{II}(SHA)].2H₂O}_n

The TG curve of the polymer shows loss of two water molecules in one step at 100–140° (mass-loss of 9% was found against 9.5% calculated). Thereafter, the coordination polymer remains stable over the temperature range 200–300° and then there is a rapid mass-loss till 480° (corresponding to thermal degradation of the polymer and consequently formation of stable metal oxide, ZnO) after which there is no further mass-loss.

(ii) {[Cd^{II}(SHA)].2H₂O}_n

The TG curve for this coordination polymer clearly indicates that the loss of two water molecules takes place at 100–180° (corresponding to 9% theoretical against 10% experimental value); further, a slow degradation of the polymer takes place upto 420° after which there is a rapid loss, indicating the degradation of coordination polymer. At 520–600°, the formation of a stable metal oxide species, CdO is evidenced, and after which no further loss is obtained.

(iii) {[Zn^{II}(AHA)].2H₂O}_n

From the TG curve, it is observed that for this coordination polymer mass-loss takes place from 100 to 140° (9% theoretical against 10% experimental value). This corresponds to a mass-loss of two lattice water molecules. There is then a gradual loss indicating degradation of coordination polymer after which the formation of a stable metal oxide is indicated.

(iv) {[Cd^{II}(AHA)].2H₂O}_n

The TG curve of this coordination polymer shows mass loss corresponding to two lattice water molecules in one step at 120–160°. There is then a gradual loss observed upto 400° after which there is

a rapid loss indicating the degradation of coordination polymer from 540 to 600°. The formation of a stable metal oxide species corresponding to CdO is evidenced at 600° after which no further mass-loss is observed.

Fig 3 DTA curve of $\{[Cd^{II}(FHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$

Mass-loss is observed at 140–180° corresponding to loss of two lattice water molecules (8% theoretical against 9% found). There is then a gradual mass-loss upto 520°, indicating the decomposition of the polymer, after which it is converted into stable metal oxide, ZnO.

Loss of two molecules in one step at 120–150° (9% theoretical against to 10% experimental) takes place for this coordination polymer. There is then a gradual mass-loss upto 400°, after which there is a rapid loss indicating the degradation of coordination

polymer. At 540–600° the formation of a stable metal oxide species, CdO is evidenced, after which no further mass-loss is observed.

According to Nikolaev *et al.*¹¹ and Singh *et al.*¹², water eliminated below 140–150° can be considered as lattice water and water eliminated above 150–180° may be that of coordination with the metal ion in chelates. In the present investigation, the water molecules are lost below 150° which indicates that in these polymers, water is present as lattice water which is further supported by infrared spectral studies.

In all these polymers, it is observed that after the loss of water of crystallisation, the further mass-loss is gradual which after higher temperature becomes rapid to finally yield stable metal oxides. The conclusions drawn by TG method had been confirmed by differential thermal analysis. As a representative system, the result of $\{[Cd^{II}(FHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$ has been shown in Fig. 3, where the endothermic peak from 55 to 165° indicates the loss of lattice water while the exothermic peak seen from 230 to 330° corresponds to the final slow decomposition of the polymer. The decomposition temperature has been evaluated to be 300°. By using thermal decomposition data and then applying Sharp-Wentworth method, the activation energy is calculated by Freeman-Carroll method (Table 3). These calculations were done after devising two computer programmes so as to reduce the personal errors. Secondly and more importantly due to

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION ENERGY AND DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE OF COORDINATION POLYMERS OF AHA, SHA AND FHA

Compd	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Activation energy (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
		Freeman-Carroll method	Sharp-Wentworth method
$\{[Cd^{II}(AHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$	340	35.70	22.46
$\{[Cd^{II}(SHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$	330	68.79	68.81
$\{[Cd^{II}(FHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$	300	10.33	16.61
$\{[Zn^{II}(AHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$	280	66.73	56.30
$\{[Zn^{II}(SHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$	300	35.70	32.74
$\{[Zn^{II}(FHA)] \cdot 2H_2O\}_n$	320	39.94	24.31

regression curve method used, the activation energy values are more accurate. Fig. 4 has been given as a representative Sharp-Wentworth plot for $\{Zn^{II}-(SHA)\cdot 2H_2O\}_n$ polymer. Similarly, thermal activation energy plot and Freeman-Carroll plot for the same coordination polymer are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Thermodynamic parameters have been calculated on the basis of thermal activation energy (Table 4). From the data given in Tables 3 and 4, it can be observed that the values of thermodynamic parameters indicate a common reaction mode. Due to abnormal low value of Z, it may be concluded that the reaction of decomposition of polychelates can be classified as a slow reaction.

Fig. 4 Sharp-Wentworth plot of $\{[Zn^{II}(SHA)]\cdot 2H_2O\}_n$.

The decomposition of the polychelates is known not to obey first order kinetics perfectly as observed by Jacobs and Tompkins¹³ and by Coats and Redfern¹⁴. These lower values are found in almost all the cases and are shown in Table 4.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies : X-ray diffraction studies have been carried out with a view to find out the type of crystal system, lattice parameters, cell volume, crystallite size of the coordination polymers. The general procedure and details of the method of calculations are based on published work¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The calculated values of hkl along with d spacing (in Å) relative intensities and observed angle have been evaluated. A complete XRD data for $\{[Cd^{II}(FHA)]\cdot 2H_2O\}_n$ polymer is given in Table 5 as a representative system. In this table however only some representative main peaks and their corresponding values have been included.

As seen, crystal lattice edge parameters corresponding to which crystal lattice edge $a = b$ is assigned, correspond to orthorhombic systems and are close to distorted tetragonal structure¹⁹.

Fig. 5. Thermal activation energy of $\{[Zn^{II}(SHA)]\cdot 2H_2O\}_n$.

The evaluated crystal parameters and other characteristics of all the coordination polymers of SHA, AHA and FHA with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} are given in Table 6.

Fig. 6 Freeman-Carroll plot of $\{[Zn^{II}(SHA)]\cdot 2H_2O\}_n$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR or pure grade quality. The solvents were double-distilled before use.

Metal estimation was done by first bridging the metal into its free state and then by using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The limit of detection for Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} was 0.002 and 0.001 ppm respectively. The metal content was further confirmed by oxide method. Carbon, hydrogen and

TABLE 4—KINETIC PARAMETERS OF COORDINATION POLYMERS OF AHA, SHA AND FHA

Compd.	Entropy change <i>S</i> (J)	Free energy change <i>F</i> (kJ)	Frequency factor <i>Z</i> (s ⁻¹)	Apparent entropy change <i>S</i> [*] (kJ)	Order of reaction <i>n</i>
{[Cd ^{II} (AHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	181.3	42.23	21.36	-75.71	0.66
{[Cd ^{II} (SHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	941.1	10.26	84.62	-51.61	0.66
{[Cd ^{II} (FHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	621.0	34.44	47.93	-74.94	0.66
{[Zn ^{II} (AHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	815.9	25.96	90.48	-50.49	0.66
{[Zn ^{II} (SHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	182.4	42.27	20.00	-43.13	0.66
{[Zn ^{II} (FHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	162.0	18.58	18.59	-76.83	1.10

TABLE 5—XRD DATA FOR {[Cd^{II}(FHA)].2H₂O}_n POLYMER

Sl. no.	2θ (Observed)	2θ (Calculated)	<i>d</i>	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max}	<i>h</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>l</i>
1.	7.200	7.20	12.267 4	45.83	0	2	0
2.	7.868	7.86	11.226 7	45.00	0	2	1
3.	8.000	8.01	11.642 4	40.83	2	1	1
4.	8.500	8.53	10.393 9	52.50	1	2	1
5.	9.500	9.52	9.301 9	43.33	1	0	3
6.	12.500	12.51	7.075 4	42.53	0	3	2
7.	12.300	12.32	7.190 0	33.33	1	2	3
8.	26.900	26.93	3.311 6	100.00	1	4	7

a = 25.350 Å
b = 24.535 Å
c = 27.852 Å
 Crystal volume = 17323.00 Å³
 Crystallite size = 173.916 deg nm⁻¹
 Crystal system = Orthorhombic

TABLE 6—CRYSTAL PARAMETERS AND OTHER CHARACTERISTICS OF COORDINATION POLYMERS OF SHA, AHA AND FHA.

Compd.	Crystal lattice edge			Unit volume Å ³	Crystallite size deg nm ⁻¹	Crystal system
	<i>a</i> (Å)	<i>b</i> (Å)	<i>c</i> (Å)			
{[Zn ^{II} (SHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	13.957	13.957	10.394	2 024.7	72.23	Tetragonal
{[Cd ^{II} (SHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	23.101	23.101	27.292	7 770.4	71.01	Tetragonal
{[Zn ^{II} (AHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	8.624	8.624	13.653	1 014.9	66.88	Tetragonal
{[Cd ^{II} (AHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	22.945	22.945	3.248	1 709.98	139.73	Tetragonal
{[Zn ^{II} (FHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	15.364	17.859	3.208	880.3	136.83	Orthorhombic*
{[Cd ^{II} (FHA)].2H ₂ O} _n	25.350	24.535	27.852	17 323.0	173.91	Orthorhombic

*Here orthorhombic is slightly distorted system.

nitrogen were analysed by a Coleman analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) was recorded in 200–4 000 cm⁻¹ region on a Perkin-Elmer 983 b spectrophotometer. The non-isothermal measurements were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 thermogravimetric analyser along with TADS computer system at

Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Nagpur University. The thermocouple used was Pt-Pt-Rh with a temperature range of 20–1000°. Sample masses ranged from 10 to 12 mg, and a furnace heating rate at 8°/min in air atmosphere was employed.

Preparation of ligands : Bis-hydroxamic acids were prepared by the modified method employed by Priyadarshini and Tandon²⁰ based on Schotten-Baumann reaction. The general methods employed in the synthesis are outlined by Yale²¹. Dicarboxylic acids (i.e. sebacic, adipic and fumaric acid) were used for the synthesis of substituted bis-hydroxamic acids. Firstly, acid dichlorides were prepared and then each was condensed with 2 moles of hydroxylamine hydrochloride separately. Dichlorides were obtained by the reaction of dry acid and thionyl chloride or phosphorus pentachloride,

These acid dichlorides so prepared were then treated with excess of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in aqueous ethanol medium containing suspension of sodium bicarbonate with constant stirring.

where, R = (CH₂)₈ for sebacyl, (CH₂)₄ for adipyl, and (CH)₂ for fumaryl. The solid so obtained was dried and recrystallised and characterised for bis-ligand.

Preparation of coordination polymers : An equimolar mixture of metal acetate and ligand was dissolved in minimum quantity of DMF and alcohol (4 : 1) mixture and refluxed for 4–5 h. The product so formed was filtered and washed with DMF and alcohol to remove excess of unreacted ligand and metal acetate. The polymer was then dried and characterised.

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